

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY AND EMPLOYEES' JOB PERFORMANCE IN SPORTS AND YOUTH DEPARTMENTS OF KERMANSHAH PROVINCE

Bahieh Zarei^{1*}, Korosh Veisi²

¹MA Student of Sport Management, Kurdistan Science and Research Branch,
Islamic Azad University, Sanandaj, Iran

²Department of Physical Education and Sport Science, Sanandaj Branch,
Islamic Azad University, Sanandaj, Iran

Abstract:

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between information technology and employees' job performance in Sports and Youth Departments of Kermanshah province. This research is a correlation study has been conducted in the field. All employees of Kermanshah province sports and youth departments have established statistical population of research (N=228), that that sample size were equalled population. For collecting research data, three standard questionnaires including Moharram Zade (2011), information technology questionnaire and Heresy & Goldsmith (1981) job performance questionnaire was used. For data analyses proper inferential statistics (K-S, Pearson Coefficient and Regression) were used. The findings showed that there is significant correlation among all dimensions of information technology with job performance of Kermanshah province sports and type variables and the use of computers, the use of computer software and internet use and the ability to predict job performance are variable. With regarding research results, it is recommended that managers of Kermanshah province sports and youth departments with proper use of information technology increase and job performance of their employees.

Keywords: information technology, job performance, Sports and Youth Departments, Kermanshah Province

¹ Correspondence: email bahiehzarei@yahoo.com

Introduction

Nowadays, performance and its determinants have absorbed the attentions of many scholars. Organizational performance is a general concept which addresses an organization's manner of execution of operations. The most agreed upon definition of performance is provided by Bourne and Neely (2003). From the view of these scholars, performance is defined as the process of explaining efficiency quality and productivity of previously done actions. According to this definition, performance is divided into two parts: 1) defines organization's manner of utilization of resources for production of goods and services. On the other hand, it refers to the relation between suitable and actual combination of input for production of specific output. 2) Effectiveness: addresses level of realization of organizational goals. These dimensions are explained in terms of suitability (level of accordance between the output and customer demands); accessibility (aspects such as abundance, supplication for prioritized groups and physical distance) and quality (level of realization of required standards) (Bourne & Neely, 2003). In addition, one of the most important indexes for describing the performance of an organization is evaluation of job performance of the employees of that organization.

Nowadays, promotion of job performance is one of the most sought objectives for managers. This is mostly because it leads to improved efficiency throughout the society and also improved national economy and improved service and product quality are other fruits of the former (Moshabaki, 1999). Job performance is defined as those routine activities which are parts of a person's job (Zakerfard, 2010). Many scholars believe that in organizations based on production of goods or providing services, job performance depends on existence of technology infrastructures, development of knowledge and customer satisfaction (Zane et al. 2003).

Among the aforementioned infrastructures, information technology is considered as the most important one (Malhotra, 2005). Information technology is considered as a strategy, thought or idea in the domain of man with innovation. By recognizing the opportunities provided by information technology, this strategy could be transformed into a practical instance or a formula. Moharampour (2012) considered four aspects for components of information technology. These aspects include using computers, using computer based software, type and amount of using the Internet and amount of using internet based services. According to this approach, information technology is considered as a new strategy for having a different access to what an organization defines. Some people consider information technology as a thought for optimal performance of affairs. A thought that makes use of an optimal combination of

hardware and software in order to establish and improve communications; while performing operations optimally (Turkiyan et al. 2013).

Making use of information technology for sharing information between customers and suppliers is creating a virtual supply chain. This new supplication chain is based on information. In addition, importance of technology and information systems is known to companies in terms of supporting current and future performance. Previous related studies show that information technology is a crucial factor for success of today's organizations.

Khalatbari et al. (2014) carried out a study and revealed that making use of IT improves employee's job performance and improves efficiency among them. Sanayei and Kahazaei (2015) elaborated on barriers of implementing IT in sports and youths department and showed that the most important ones among these barriers include financial, technical, behavioural and organizational barriers. Not unlike other organizations, sports based organizations are experiencing a new era of competition. In order to improve their employees' job performance, these organizations need to pay more attention to elements such as information technology and organizational agility.

Foki (2009) has conducted a study and answered the question that if It can improve efficiency? This study has investigated the relation between information technology and improvement of efficiency between 1975 and 2005. The conclusion of this study implies that from the year 2000 on, a large portion of improvements in efficiency were resulted from implementation of information technology.

Badesco (2009) performed a study conducted a study and elaborated on effects of information technology on efficiency among Spanish firms. Results of this study revealed that efficiency of workforce is significantly sensitive towards changes in amount and intensity of technology capital. Results of this study have also shown that although that in certain periods the efficiency has been improved, but this influence is not considerably resulted from investing on information technology.

Not unlike any other organizations, sports based organizations too need to improve their employees' performance through different methods and approaches. In this regard, information technology can play a beneficial role in this regard. On the other hand, information technology and its effects on other organizational variables have been less frequently considered by sports scholars. On this basis and considering the aforementioned content, the researcher of this study is about to find an answer for the question that what is the relation between information technology and job performance in Sports and youth department of Kermanshah province?

Materials and Methods

This study is a descriptive-correlative study and its required data are gathered through field methods. The population of the study includes the entire employees of Kermanshah Province's departments of sports and youth as 228 individuals. Since the population was limited, the entire population was selected as the sample size. Data collection instruments of the study include Moharram Pour's standardized information technology survey including 28 items in four dimensions of using computers, using computer based software, type and amount of using the Internet and amount of using internet based services; and standardized job performance questionnaire of Hersey and Goldsmith (1981) including 16 items based on 5 degrees Likert scale in seven dimensions of ability, role transparency, support, motivation, feedback, credit and environment). In order to determine the questionnaires' validity, they were exposed to five professors of physical education. In addition, the reliability of the former questionnaires was calculated through Cronbach's alpha coefficient method. For the questionnaire of information technology the Cronbach's alpha value was calculated as 0.89 and for the questionnaire of job performance, this value was calculated as 0.78.

Descriptive and inferential statistics (Pearson's correlation coefficient and the Regression test) were used for analysis of findings of the study. The data were analysed through the SPSS software and the entire statistical tests were run at significance range of 0.001.

Findings

With respect to results of demographic part of the study, 53.5% of the respondents aged between 31 to 40 years; 52.26% held a B.A; 41.22 percent had between 1 to 5 years of experience; 55.7% of the respondents were educated in human sciences and arts and 75% are among the organizational rank of employee. The average and standard deviation of the variable of type and amount of using the internet are respectively 16.1 and 4.74; for amount of using internet services these values are 20.4 and 5.2; for information technology 68.22 and 15.68; for ability 11.14 and 2.53; for support 7.25 and 1.98; for motivation 10.76 and 2.73; for feedback 7.31 and 1.94; for credit 6.77 and 2.24; for environment 6.87 and 2.3 and for job performance 57.45 and 11.85.

Table 1: Correlation coefficients of information technology and its dimensions and job performance among employees of sports and youth departments of Kermanshah province

Sig.	Job performance (JP)	Variable
0.000	0.51**	Type and amount of using computer
0.000	0.55**	Using computer based software
0.000	0.45**	Type and amount of using Internet
0.000	0.37**	Amount of using internet services
0.000	0.55**	Information technology
p < 0.001**		

As you can see in table 1, results of the Pearson test have shown that a significant relation holds among dimensions of information technology and job performance among employees. This results means that by increasing the employees' knowledge about utilization of computers, software and internet based services, their job performance increases.

In order to indicate the extent of effectiveness of each of IT dimensions on job performance among employees, the step by step regression test is performed and the following table summarizes the results.

Table 2: Model estimation results in terms of anticipation of job performance

Independent variable: job performance				Explanatory variable
P- value	T statistic	Beta coefficient	Coefficient	
0.979	1.612	-	-0.005	Constant
0.000	3.88	0.267	0.334	Type and amount of using computers
0.000	13.65	0.62	0.709	Using software
0/000	4.73	0.485	0.521	Internet usage type and extent
0.118	1.14	0.68	0.023	Internet services usage extent
264.15				F statistic
0.000				P-value
0.378				R ²
0.371				R ² adjusted
1.547				Durbin-Watson

According to table 2, the coefficient for type and amount of utilizing computers is 0.267; for using computer based software its 0.62 and for type and amount of using the Internet, its 0.485. According to results, the obtained determination coefficient for the dependent variable of job performance is equal to 0.378 and it shows that 37.85 of the

changes in job performance are anticipated by changes in type and amount of using computers, using computer based software and type and amount of utilizing the Internet. Since the Durbin-Watson statistic is located in the range between 1.5 and 2.5, therefore the residues could be considered independent. According to the above table, the calculated significance for this statistic of F is equal to 0.000 and it shows the significance of the regression at confidence level of 95%. With respect to aforementioned indexes, the model is of suitable efficiency and that the variables of using computers, using computer based software, type and amount of using the Internet and amount of using internet based services are able to anticipate the variable of job performance.

The regression equation can be written in the following form:

$$Y = 0.334 (\text{type and amount of using computers}) + 0.709 (\text{using computer based software}) + 0.521 (\text{amount of using the Internet}).$$

Discussion and Conclusion

Results of this research have shown that a significant relation exists between IT and its dimensions and job performance among employees of sports and youths departments of Kermanshah Province. In addition it was shown that variables of using computers, using computer based software, type and amount of using the Internet and amount of using internet based services are able to anticipate the variable of job performance. This finding is consistent with findings obtained by Khalatbari et al. (2011); Foki (2009) and Badesco (2009). The current era is the era of accelerated changes and lack of certainty about future and lack of available information for decision making. There are changes that if the organization is unable to keep its pace with them, it will face difficulties and even bankruptcy. On this basis, organizations should always have this one constant feature: continuous evolution and adaptation. This element is the main key in learning organizations. Creating a learning environment and increasing the competence and capabilities of human resources are the necessities of creating a learning firm. Human resource management provides knowledge management with a context in which obtaining information and knowledge becomes institutionalized throughout the entire organization. With respect to importance of new knowledge in terms of success of modern organizations, information and communication technologies are of greater importance. Advances in the section of information and communications technology has led to formation of new opportunities in businesses, reduction of costs and improved effectiveness and efficiency among the employees. Nowadays, the domain of

IT is rapidly growing and its infrastructures are also rapidly developing. In addition, employees have been provided with a better access to these tools. This is while other expenses of the organization including energy, raw material, wages and other production related costs are rapidly increasing. On this basis, making use of information technology can result in several different applications in terms of occupation of employees. Managers of today's organizations are well aware that not only for obtaining goals, but also for obtaining a sustainable competitive advantage, the organization and its entire employees require information and communication technologies. On this basis it must be inferred that an organization's implementation of related information and communication technologies can improve employees' job performance. Considering these and the entire aforementioned content, we recommend providing employees with computers, instructing employees for making use of the Internet, instructing employees regarding working with data bases and instructing them to use digital libraries. In addition, we recommend making use of utilities and software for performing daily affairs, managers' support from using information and communication technology based systems in sports and youths departments, persuading employees towards making use of new information and having more contact with co-workers and customers through e-mail, chatting and social networks. On the other hand, future researchers are recommended to investigate the relation between information technology and other organizational elements including efficiency of employees, job satisfaction and organizational performance. They are also recommended to investigate other effective elements on job performance among employees of Kermanshah Province's sports and youth departments including organizational support, organizational learning and empowerment of employees.

References

1. Chen, J., Yang, K. F., & Tang, F. I. (2014). Applying the technology acceptance model to explore public health nurses' intentions towards web based learning: A cross-sectional questionnaire survey. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 45, 869–878.
2. Malhotra, Y. (2005). Integrating knowledge management technologies in organizational business processes: getting real time enterprises to deliver real business performance. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 9(1), 7-28.

3. Moharramipour, Akram. (2011). Effects of information technology to increase productivity in the food industry Zanjan province. School of Management, Islamic Azad University of Abhar.
4. Moshabaki, Ali. (1998). the relationship between organizational structure and job performance Education in Tehran. Master's Thesis, School of Management, Tehran University.
5. Sanayei, Ali and Khazaeipool, J. (2014). Analysis of the barriers in implementing IT departments of Youth and Sports in Fars province using fuzzy approach Chndmyar decision. *Journal of Sport Management*, 6(2), 341-325.
6. Swafford, P. M., Ghosh, S., & Murthy, N. (2008). Achieving supply chain agility through IT in tegration and flexibility. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 116(2), 288-297.
7. Tallon, P. P. (2008). Inside the adaptive enterprise: an information technology capabilities perspective on business process agility. *Information Technology and Management*, 9(1), 21-36.
8. Torkiyan, K., Khorvash, M., & Tabaeiyan, A. (2013). On the Relationship of Applying Information Technology with Organizational Agility in Youth Sports Organizations of Esfahan Province. *International Journal of Sport Studies*, 4(12), 1546-1550.
9. Zain, M., Kassim, N. M., & Mokhtar, E. (2003). Using information technology and information systems for organizational agility in Malaysian firms. *Singapore Management Review*, 25(1), 69-83.
10. Zakir Fard, Mehdi. (2009). The impact of cognitive skills training shift supervisor satisfaction and job performance. *Contemporary Psychology*, 6, 22-16.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).